

D3.2 Innovation Hub: First Release

Project	PoliRural	
Project title:	Future Oriented Collaborative Policy Development for Rural Areas and People	
Grant	818496	
Website:	www.polirural.eu	
Contact:	info@polirural.eu	
Version:	2.0	
Date:	30 April 2021	
Responsible:	CCSS	
Contributing Partners:	Jiri Kvapil, Petr Uhlir, Frantisek Zadrazil (CCSS) Ota Cerba, Pavel Hajek (P4A) Raitis Berzins, Michal Kepka (BOSC) Sarka Horakova (CoO)	
Reviewers:	Runar Bergheim (Avinet) Tomas Mildorf (P4A)	
Dissemination Level:	Public	X
	Confidential - only consortium members and European Commission Services	
Keywords:	Digital Innovation Hub, Social Space, Rural Development, Visualisation, Jupyter Notebook, Attractiveness of Regions	

Revision History

Revision no.	Date	Author	Organization	Description
0.1	20/02/2020	Sarka Horakova	CoO	Initial template
0.2	20/02/2020	Karel Charvat	CCSS	Initial TOC
0.3	24/03/2020	Ota Cerba, Pavel Hajek, Petr Uhlir, Jiri Kvapil, Frantisek Zadrazil, Raitis Berzins, Michal Kepka	CCSS, P4A, BOSC, CoO	Contribution of chapters
0.4	25/03/2020	Karel Charvat	CCSS	Final draft
1.0	31/03/2020	Karel Charvat	CCSS	Final
1.1.	31/03/2021	Jiri Kvapil	CCSS	Project reviewers' comments processed
1.2	16/04/2021	Pavel Kogut	21C	Internal reviewer's comments
2.0	30/04/2021	Jiri Kvapil	CCSS	Final version

Responsibility for the information and views set out in this publication lies entirely with the authors.

Responsibility for the information and views set out in this publication lies entirely with the authors.

Every effort has been made to ensure that all statements and information contained herein are accurate, however the PoliRural Project Partners accept no liability for any error or omission.

Table of Contents

List of Tables	4
List of Figures	4
List of Acronyms	5
Executive Summary	7
Keywords	7
1 Introduction	8
2 Concept	9
3 Basic architecture	10
3.1 Context of Innovation Hub in PoliRural	10
3.2 Digital Innovation Hub Reference Architecture	10
4 Design of user interfaces of the DIH	13
4.1 Overall design	13
4.2 Liferay	14
5 Map client	15
6 Backend implementation	17
6.1 Philosophy	17
6.2 Cloud implementation	20
6.3 Description of single components	21
7 Data available	23
7.1 Internal Plan4all data	23
7.1.1 SPOI	23
7.1.2 Open Land Use	23
7.1.3 Open Transport Map	24
7.2 External data	25
7.2.1 Eurostat	25
8 Demo applications	27
8.1 Overall design	27
8.1.1 Concept	27
8.1.2 Backend description	30
8.1.3 User interface.....	31

8.2	Region clustering	32
8.2.1	Algorithmus development.....	32
8.2.2	Front end development	32
8.3	Best Practice Atlas	33
9	How to access	35
9.1	Open Access	35
9.2	Administration for frontend users	35
9.3	Pilot sections	35
9.4	Account setting	36
9.5	Editing social media and tools	37
9.5.1	Content and Knowledge base - Science Shop	37
9.5.2	Forum	38
9.5.3	Wiki	38
9.5.4	Blog.....	39
9.6	Access to JupyterHub	40
10	Conclusion	42

List of Tables

Table 1	Available EUROSTAT data	27
Table 2	Region clustering	32

List of Figures

Figure 1	Polirural workflow	10
Figure 1c	Context of Innovation Hub within PoliRural ecosystem of technical components	
Figure 2	Innovation Hub Reference Architecture	12
Figure 3	Overall design	13
Figure 4	PoliRural Map Client.....	17
Figure 5	Dynamic model integration.....	17
Figure 6	Jupyter Notebook utilisation	18
Figure 7	Working with models using Jupyter Notebook.....	19

Figure 8 Using applications outside of platform	20
Figure 9 PoliRural backend design	20
Figure 10 Jupyter Notebook interface	21
Figure 11 Components on PoliRural Hub	22
Figure 12 SPOI data	23
Figure 13 Open Land Use data	24
Figure 14 Open Transport Map	25
Figure 15 Attractiveness Data Composition	27
Figure 16 Input data preparation	28
Figure 17 Example of Attractiveness map.....	29
Figure 18 Next work	29
Figure 19 Interface for Attractiveness calculation	31
Figure 20 Region Data Visualisation.....	31
Figure 21 Best Practice Atlas I	34
Figure 22 Best Practice Atlas II	34
Figure 23 Administration menu for registered users.....	35
Figure 24 Editing menu	36
Figure 25 Profile of user setting	36
Figure 26 Science shop	37
Figure 27 Science shop - adding new thread	37
Figure 28 Science shop - thread example	38
Figure 29 Wiki - adding new page	39
Figure 30 Wiki - short codes.....	39
Figure 31 Blog - Adding new post.....	40
Figure 32 Jupyter Notebook access.....	41
Figure 33 Visualisation data with Jupyter	41

List of Acronyms

API = Application Programming Interface

BBP = Bio based Products and Processes

BPA - Best Practice Atlas

CMS = Content Management System

CSV = Comma-separated value

DIH = PoliRural Digital Innovation Hub

DIH = Digital Innovation Hub

EIP Agri = Agricultural European Innovation Partnership

GUI = Graphical User Interface

HILUCS = Hierarchical INSPIRE Land Use Classification System

HTML = Hypertext Markup Language

IT = Information Technology

LPIS = Land Parcel Identification System

NAT = Network Address Translation

NG = Next Generation

OGC = Open Geospatial Consortium

ORDBMS = object-relational database management system

OTN = OpenTransportNet

PC = Personal Computer

RAI = Rural Attractiveness Index

RDBMS = Relational Database Management System

RDF = Resource Description Framework

SEO = Search Engine Optimization

SPARQL = Simple Protocol and RDF Query Language

SPOI = Smart Points of Interest

UX = User Experience

VLAN = Virtual Local Area Network

WMC = Web Content Management

WMS = Web Map Service

XML = eXtensible Markup Language

Executive Summary

The aim of the PoliRural Digital Innovation Hub (DIH) is to offer a public user interface and introduction to the *innovations* of the project. To this end, the DIH entry point is built on a content management system. Furthermore, the DIH will provide four distinctive sections, or *spaces*, that cater for both internal and external users:

1. An interaction space with forums, dialogue and Wiki capabilities to support stakeholder interaction
2. A learning space for Massive Open Online Courses to facilitate dissemination and uptake of knowledge and methodology developed through the project
3. An experimentation space for testing analytics and visualization including text mining and system dynamics based on real data
4. A development and hosting space for creating virtual instances of the shared reference to be used by each pilot when developing their applications.

Below these high-level functional requirements there is a lot of implicit functionality that in some cases can be supplied by more than one technology component. In order to identify how the DIH can best serve the pilots, the deliverable starts off by a detailed analysis of pilots in terms of context, data availability and requirements, analytics requirements and pre-existing tools and technologies that the DIH must be capable of interfacing with.

Based on the design of PoliRural Digital Innovation Hub in **D3.1 Innovation Hub Technical Specification** the first release of PoliRural DIH was implemented.

Currently, this release contains:

- CMS Liferay with set of Social Tools: science shop, blog post, forum, wiki and library
- Maps client
- First demo applications
- First Pan European Data sets ready for experimentation
- Cloud based tools for preparing own analysis and managing own data

Keywords

Digital Innovation Hub, Social Space, Rural Development, Visualisation, Jupyter Notebook, Attractiveness of Regions

1 Introduction

A Digital Innovation Hub is a multi-actor ecosystem that supports communities in their digital transformation by providing a broad variety of services from a one-stop shop. The purpose of a DIH is to:

- provide a social space for community of practices;
- provide access to digital technologies and competencies;
- provide access to infrastructure and tests digital innovations (“test before invest”);
- provide development playground for map based projects;
- offer training and skills development;
- offer support in finding finance for digital transformation;
- help in networking and connecting users and suppliers of digital innovations;

The main goal of this activity during the PoliRural project is to design and develop a prototype of a Digital Innovation Hub. This DIH should integrate technology, datasets and libraries in one infrastructure with a complex user-oriented portal in the Web environment. The user portal should provide general principles of the content management framework as well as principles of social space by providing a blog, forum, science shop, wiki pages etc. The DIH should be able to connect end users with developers or researchers to improve the impact of the demo applications or case studies by short-chain feedback from end-users. End users can join larger communities around the DIH to get advice, cooperation potential and access to modern technologies utilization.

The prototype of the DIH is based on a cloud solution where Liferay is providing user portal framework and background for front-end applications while OpenStack provides a back-end environment where many libraries for data analyses, data storage and data publishing are installed.

2 Concept

The PoliRural Digital innovation Hub is an integration platform where all technologies, approaches and people meet. It is a central point for knowledge exchange and transfer. Strong involvement of pilots is one of key cornerstones supporting the overall project goal. There is a strong vision and tight position of the DIH within the project. The overall project progress in three phases is reflected in DIH development and new tools and outputs are continuously added in the DIH.

Figure 1 Polirural workflow

DIH is not only an isolated component of the PoliRural project, but its ambition is also to communicate with sister projects (RURALIZATION, DEMETER), exchanging methodologies, tools and knowledge, organizing cross-project seminars, and connecting project communities. Cooperation with related projects within the framework of Digital innovation Hubs (SmartAgriHubs, SIEUSOIL) is planned providing incubating environment for development of future tools and software, providing opensource components, reusable map services and data to build on.

3 Basic architecture

3.1 Context of Innovation Hub in PoliRural

The DIH is distinctive from three other components in the PoliRural digital ecosystem (Figure 1):

- The home page (a website with a content management system)
- The semantic explorer (a ready-made application for exploring semantic graphs)
- The system dynamics tool (a commercial off the shelf authoring tool and a number of published, configurable models)

Figure 2a Context of Innovation Hub within PoliRural ecosystem of technical components

3.2 Digital Innovation Hub Reference Architecture

The technical platform of the innovation hub is described as a reference architecture that can be realized in three different ways:

1. As a central service provider, shared data and components node
2. As a centralized pilot node hosted in the PoliRural private cloud

3. As a decentralized pilot node hosted in a legacy environment

This approach permits the innovation hub architecture to be applicable to both new and legacy IT environments. We believe this approach is superior to a make-or-break monolithic system that must be identical in every way, shape and form. (see Figure 2).

- The box denoted [Development space] is a placeholder for the cloud hosting sub-system that is described in greater detail in the following chapter.
- The components shown as boxes in the diagram above will be available for inclusion in centrally hosted and decentralized pilot instances of the Innovation Hub platform as Docker images. The components included reflect common requirements identified through the analysis of the preliminary pilot descriptions and data requirements outlined in chapter 3 above. The specific functions provided by each component and how it resolves specific needs is described in chapter 7 below.
- Boxes shown in grey colour are external to the innovation hub application system and will be dealt with as third-party integrations as required.

This part is originally from **D3.1 Innovation Hub Technical Specification**. In next chapters implementation is demonstrated

Figure 3 Innovation Hub Reference Architecture

4 Design of user interfaces of the DIH

The frontend layout of the DIH portal (figure 3) is based on the wireframe for better UX usage and is implemented into the Liferay portal framework. Responsive design based on the Bootstrap framework is used for optimal viewing and navigation across a wide range of devices, including traditional PC, tablet and surface, smartphones, and all other mobile devices. Also semantic code for better SEO and application of the SEO principles.

4.1 Overall design

Figure 4 Overall design

4.2 Liferay

Liferay Portal provides a robust platform to build a website on quickly and serve it to all clients - desktop, mobile, or anything in between. It provides all the standard applications which are needed. It also provides an easy to use development framework for new applications or customization.

Liferay's collaboration suite resonates with apps and features that foster excellent communication. Its Message Boards app gives users a platform for discussions, questions and answers, and comments. Blogs publish user's ideas using rich content, so readers can understand them clearly and respond to them. Collaboration is enhanced in all these applications through mentioning other users—tagging them by name to get their attention or give them kudos.

CMS - page editor - Liferay Portal's Web Content Management (WCM) system allows non-technical users to publish content to the web without having advanced knowledge of web technology or programming of any sort. Liferay WCM empowers users to publish their own content with a simple point and click interface and it helps them keep the site fresh.

With Liferay Portal's WCM, users have the ability to create, edit, stage, approve, and publish content with easy-to-learn yet powerful tools. Liferay's WCM streamlines the content creation process for end users. It's much faster to use Liferay's WCM than it would be to create all the content for your site in HTML. WCM is integrated with Liferay's services so advanced template developers can use them to query for data stored elsewhere in Liferay.

- **WYSIWYG Editor:** A complete HTML editor that allows users to modify fonts, add color, insert images, and much more.
- **Structure Editor:** Easily add and remove fields users want available to content creators and then dynamically move them around. This editor includes an entire suite of form controls you can drag and drop onto your structure.
- **Template Editor:** Import template script files or create their own template that informs the system how to display the content within the fields determined by the structure.
- **Web Content Display:** An application that lets users place web content on a page in a website.

- **Asset Publisher:** An application which can aggregate different types of content together in one view. This app is covered in more detail in the Publishing Assets section.
- **Scheduler:** Lets users schedule when content is reviewed, displayed and removed. This feature is covered in more detail in the Scheduling Web Content Publication section.
- **Workflow Integration:** Run users content through an approval or review process. This feature is covered in more detail in the Using Workflow section.

Collaboration - Liferay Portal ships with a robust suite of collaboration applications that can be used to build communities of users for the website. These applications provide all the features that would be expected of standalone applications outside a portal setting. The difference with Liferay's collaboration apps, however, is that they all share a common look and feel, security model, and architecture.

Available apps on Liferay and all the components of Liferay's Collaboration suite:

- Blogs
- Message Boards
- Wikis
- Announcements
- Mail
- Knowledge Bases
- Bookmarks

Media manager - Liferay Portal's Documents and Media library provides a mechanism for storing files online using the same type of structure that is used to store files locally. It serves as a virtual shared drive, and can mount and browse external repositories. Its companion app, the Media Gallery, displays selected content from the Documents and Media library. It can display image, audio, and video files. Other features in the Documents and Media library include customizable document types and metadata sets, automatic document preview generation, and support for mounting multiple external repositories.

5 Map client

The Map is one of the central functions of Hub. The Map client is based on HSLayers NG. Link to GitHub <https://github.com/hslayers/hslayers-ng>

HSLayers NG (<https://ng.hslayers.org/>) is a web mapping library written in JavaScript. It extends OpenLayers 4 functionality and takes basic ideas from the previous HSLayers library, but uses modern JS frameworks instead of ExtJS 3 at the frontend and provides better adaptability. That's why the NG ("Next Generation") is added to its name. It is still under development and provided as open source. HSLayers is built in a modular way which enables the modules to be freely attached and removed as far as the dependencies for each of them are satisfied. The dependency checking is done automatically. (Figure 4).

The core of the framework is developed using AngularJS, requireJS and Bootstrap. This combination of frameworks was chosen mainly for providing fast and scalable development and for providing modern responsive layout of application.

The most important modules are:

- Map: The map functionality is provided by OpenLayers4 and extended by some controls like navigation bar, scale line, attribution dialog, GPS and compass tracking etc. It supports multi-touch gestures, but the performance is highly dependent on the browser and mobile device hardware.
- Layer manager and legend: Layer manager is used for listing all the map layers, displaying or hiding them and setting the transparency. The user can view layers metadata and attribution by clicking on it. A legend is fetched from the server and displayed in a separate panel for all the wms layers on the map. Grouping of layers in containers is also provided which enables a more user friendly and organized representation of layers for
- OGC Web Services parser: This is used for GetCapabilities requests to different map servers and parsing the response. It can then be used for automatic or user initiated generation of map layers only by knowing the URL to the specific OGC standardized map service.
- Linked Open Data explorer: Eurostat explorer is a demo application (module) which queries Semantic Web data sources via SPARQL endpoints. It demonstrates the feasibility of automatic query building for Eurostat report data and displaying it on a map of NUTS2 regions (specified in GeoJSON file) according to the calculated transparency ratios. On the server side it uses a Virtuoso Universal Server which is a middleware and database engine hybrid that combines the functionality of a traditional RDBMS, ORDBMS, virtual database, RDF, XML, free-text, web application server and file server functionality in a single system.

Figure 5 PoliRural Map Client

6 Backend implementation

6.1 Philosophy

A platform to facilitate experimentation and data science oriented tasks as well as publishing prototype applications has been developed by BOSC. We call it DIH Lab in this document. It showcases system dynamics models and in future will also provide running it with different parameters. (Figure 5)

Figure 6 Dynamic model integration

The main building blocks of the DIH are:

- Dashboard
- External apps (mainly maps)

- List of datasets with descriptions
- Workspaces
- Models (System dynamics)
- Maps for calculating and displaying of rural attractiveness and clusterization of regions

The DIH Lab is a platform where users can have their own isolated docker based environment to perform data science related tasks involving data mining, processing and visualization. (Figure 6)

Figure 7 Jupyter Notebook utilisation

To provide this functionality JupyterHub platform has been tightly integrated into the DIH Lab by developing user account synchronization, Jupyter notebook transferring, execution using Papermill and chaining of outputs and visualizing them using one or a combination of methods:

- Maps based on Hslayers-ng mapping library
- Data tables
- Images
- Plain text output

Figure 8 Working with models using Jupyter Notebook

A visual modelling tool has been developed to make the process of chaining the building blocks of data-processing-pipeline easier. Linking datasets to processing nodes, generates code in the Jupyter notebook which is behind each processing node. (Figure 7)

Currently it is possible to run notebooks which import the most common data science related libraries, such as *geojson*, *datapackage*, *pandas*, *plotly*, *geopandas*, *chart-studio*, *matplotlib*, *descartes*, *scikit-learn*, but further extension of this list will be done after initial feedback from the users. Also more work will be needed to support the various output types it is possible to generate using jupyter notebooks and mapping output to visualization components.

Applications can be also developed outside this platform and deployed later by providing a git repository URL. The applications run inside an isolated docker container behind a reverse proxy provided by the Hub infrastructure. This way it will be possible to use the vast amount of data on the server without needing to download it on developer's machines. (Figure 8)

Figure 9 Using applications outside of platform

6.2 Cloud implementation

Internal cloud solution is run on own managed and dedicated servers in a location of Prague, Czech Republic and as such is under full control of Lesprojekt - sluzby company. It is built on OpenStack software, based on Linux operating systems and other open source technologies. (Figure 9)

Figure 10 PoliRural backend design

OpenStack enables optimal usage of hardware resources joining standalone servers in a seamless cloud under a single management. It provides a vast number of services including virtualisation, block device sharing, distributed computing, support to various docking technologies, etc. A very strong network stack allows for low level network isolation including VLAN support, NAT and integrated firewall. Fine grained user management enables

logical segmentation of OpenStack instances into standalone independent instances as if they were run on separate physical servers.

Administrator has a very good overview of current use of hardware resources due to strong reporting capabilities and a web dashboard.

Backup is done at least weekly, for critical infrastructure even more frequently. Own backup infrastructure managed by Lesprojekt - sluzby company.

New virtual servers are rapidly deployed within minutes as requested by our users. Various operating systems are prepared as snapshots for instant use. (Figure 10)

The screenshot shows the OpenStack dashboard for the 'Lesprojekt' project. The 'Instance' page is active, displaying a table of 4 instances. The table columns are: Název instance, Název obrazu, IP adresa, Typ, Klíč, Stav, Zóna dostupnosti, Úloha, Stav napájení, Age, and Činnost. The instances listed are:

Název instance	Název obrazu	IP adresa	Typ	Klíč	Stav	Zóna dostupnosti	Úloha	Stav napájení	Age	Činnost
polirural-jupyter	ubuntu_18.04	10.0.0.119	c2.m4.d50	jka	Aktivní	nova	Žádný	Běží	1 měsíc, 2 týdny	Vytvořit snapshot
polirural-layman	layman-cisty	10.0.0.118	c2.m4.d50	jka	Aktivní	nova	Žádný	Běží	1 měsíc, 3 týdny	Vytvořit snapshot
polirural-cat	-	10.0.0.117	c2.m2.d50	jka	Aktivní	nova	Žádný	Běží	1 měsíc, 3 týdny	Vytvořit snapshot
polirural-hub	centos8-stream	10.0.0.116	c2.m4.d50	jka	Aktivní	nova	Žádný	Běží	2 měsíce, 3 týdny	Vytvořit snapshot

Figure 11 Jupyter Notebook interface

Polirural Hub is based on technologies described in the following section.

6.3 Description of single components

Liferay Portal Community Edition – frontend and portal solution, main collaboration tool. Used for registration and authentication of users, publication of news, interactive communication with users using Forum, Blog and other networking tools. (Figure 11)

JupyterHub - server based tool available via web browser interface, using Python, R and other tools and libraries. Used for creation of own data management processes, data analysis and visualisations in cloud environment

Figure 12 Components on PoliRural Hub

OpenMicka - metadata catalogue for spatial data storage, organisation, searching and publication using CSW service. Available on GitHub <https://github.com/hsrs-cz/Micka>

Layman – spatial data management, upload and publication tool, supports publication of standardised WMS and other OGC services. Published on GitHub <https://github.com/jirik/layman>

SensLog – web-based or cloud-based tool for sensor data management, gathering, storage, export and visualisation. Its data structure can be adjusted to any sensor data standard. GitHub link <https://github.com/mkepka/senslog>

Python - high level scripting language supporting high extensibility and modularity. Web: www.python.org

Anaconda - Python distribution focused on scientific and statistical computing. Contains packages for machine learning, data manipulation, visualisation and presentation. Web: www.anaconda.com

TensorFlow - machine learning platform consisting of sets of tools and libraries originally developed by Google. Web: www.tensorflow.org

Keras - open-source neural network library written in Python. It is capable of running on top of TensorFlow or other machine learning platforms. Web: <https://keras.io>

GDAL - library for handling spatial data, both raster and vector. Supports many geometric, arithmetic and statistical tools with bindings to many programming languages including Python, C and many more. Web: <https://gdal.org/>

Pandas - Python library for data analysis, including its **GeoPandas** extension providing spatial data analysis and manipulation tools mostly based on GDAL functionalities. Web: <https://pandas.pydata.org/>

R - statistical computing platform and programming language supporting many deeply focused plugins for various domain applications. Web: www.r-project.org

7 Data available

7.1 Internal Plan4all data

7.1.1 SPOI

The Smart Points of Interest dataset is the seamless and open resource of POIs that is available for other users to download, search or reuse in applications and services. Its principal target is to provide information as Linked data together with other data sets. The added value of the Smart approach in comparison to other similar solutions consists in implementation of linked data, using standardized and respected datatype properties and development of the completely harmonized data set with uniform data model and common classification. Web: <https://gis.zcu.cz/spoi/> (Figure 12).

Figure 13 SPOI data

7.1.2 Open Land Use

The base European dataset is derived from the set of available data sources that are helping identify the land use in particular locality. The list of the sources used so far on the Pan-European level includes Urban Atlas and CORINE Land Cover. Where available, there are

datasets such as Cadaster data, Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) or any other suitable datasets incorporated into the Open Land Use, particularly for the Czech Republic, Austria or Flanders region.

The data are open and they are available for downloading. It is harmonized towards Hierarchical INSPIRE Land Use Classification System (HILUCS). The resulting dataset is composed of global pan-European data combined where available with regional often highly precise data. In this way we provide the most precise land-use map without any gaps.

Web: https://sdi4apps.eu/open_land_use/ (Figure 13)

Figure 14 Open Land Use data

7.1.3 Open Transport Map

The Open Transport Map displays a road network which is suitable for routing and visualizes average daily Traffic Volumes for the whole EU on the main roads (highways, speedways and first class roads). It also visualizes daytime related Traffic Volumes in OTN Pilot Cities (Antwerp, Birmingham, Issy-le-Moulineaux, Liberec region). Technically, the Open Transport Map can serve as a map itself as well as a layer embedded in your map, it is derived from the most popular open dataset OpenStreetMap, it is accessible via both GUI and API and it covers the whole European Union. Web: <http://opentransportmap.info/> (Figure 14)

Figure 15 Open Transport Map

7.2 External data

7.2.1 Eurostat

Description	NUTS level	Year	Number of records
Percentage of the population rating their satisfaction as high, medium or low by domain, sex, age and educational attainment level; Only low satisfaction is stored -- inverse order (lower values are positive).	0	2013	1478
Average rating of satisfaction by domain, sex, age and educational attainment level.	0	2011	1478
Population on 1 January by broad age group, sex and NUTS 3 region; Ratio of population with age less than 15 years and total population.	3	2018	1520
Crude marriage rate per 1000 persons.	0	2017	1340

Projected old-age dependency ratio per 100 persons.	0	2018	1394
The indicator measures total national emissions of the so-called 'Kyoto basket' of greenhouse gases. The average population of the reference year (calculated as the arithmetic mean of the population on 1st January of two consecutive years) is used as a denominator (per capita).	0	2017	1476
Number of high-tech patent applications to the EPO by priority year by NUTS 3 regions.	3	2012	762
Estimated soil erosion by water (tonnes per hectare).	3	2012	770
All persons directly responsible for the holding and/or working on the holding.	2	2013	733
Organic farming: number of farms	2	2013	733
Municipal waste by NUTS 2 regions (thousand tonnes)	2	2013	831
General government expenditure (COFOG) - Recreation, culture and religion, % from GDP	0	2017	1394
Gross domestic product (GDP) at current market prices by NUTS 3 regions	3	2017	324
Real growth rate of regional gross value added (GVA) at basic prices by NUTS 2 regions - percentage change on previous year.	2	2017	1133
Long-term total unemployment rate	0	2018	1509
General government expenditure by function (Percentage of gross domestic product)	0	2017	1394
The indicator balance represents the total potential threat to the environment of nitrogen surplus or deficit in agricultural soils. The unit	0	2015	1392

of measure used is kg of nutrient per hectare of this land.			
The indicator balance represents the total potential threat to the environment of phosphorous surplus or deficit in agricultural soils. The unit of measure used is kg of nutrient per hectare of this land.	0	2015	1392
Final consumption expenditure of households, by recreation and culture	0	2017	1513

Table 1 Available EUROSTAT data

8 Demo applications

8.1 Overall design

8.1.1 Concept

Support of rural regions is one of the crucial roles of global society over the world. Successful and vital rural regions can help with many burning problems threatening the human population such as climate change, poverty, hunger or clean energy. The efficient and targeted support is dependent on a high-quality assessment of the potential of particular regions. This potential can be termed as rural attractiveness. (Figure 15)

Number of datasets

Figure 16 Attractiveness Data Composition

The rural attractiveness follows many factors, which mean various views on particular regions. These views include, for example, nature, economy, culture or society. Therefore a quantification of rural attractiveness has to be understood as an example of multiple-criteria

decision analysis. For the mapping of rural attractiveness, the set of six factors was selected. These factors are published in deliverable D1.1 Envisioning More Attractive Rural Places & Professions of the PoliRural project. The factors of rural attractiveness used in the development of pan-European maps are (in alphabetical order): Anthropic, Cultural, Economic, Institutional, Natural and Social & Human.

The map shows rural attractiveness of NUTS3 regions in Europe. The presentation of the total regional rural attractiveness (as an index) represents the global view to the question of assessment of the potential of country territories. The map visualizes the so-called Rural Attractiveness Index (RAI). The RAI is calculated as an average of particular relevant values from input data sets.

There is a high number of input data for maps. These datasets are very heterogeneous from the view of quality. Therefore it is crucial to present an indicator of data quality as well to be able to consider the reliability of provided information. The data quality in case of RAI consider the age of data, detail (NUTS level) and occurrence of data values in particular regions. (Figure 16).

Figure 17 Input data preparation

The current version of the map contains normalized data from 27 datasets. (Figure 17)

Figure 18 Example of Attractiveness map

The further development includes (Figure 19).

- searching, collecting and harmonizing new input datasets,
- implementation of weighted average based on weights derived from stakeholders’ survey and quality of input data,
- optimization (filtering) of input datasets based on statistical assessment (correlation),
- involvement of cluster calculation enabling the finding of regions with similar characteristics.

Figure 19 Next work

8.1.2 Backend description

Back-end part of the application is realized as a single web service implemented in Express.js. The data source is a CSV file with all the statistical datasets merged into it. One row equals one NUTS region and cells of the row represent normalized values for each dataset.

The service provides four methods:

- GET /refresh - can be used to reload cached data when the CSV changes
- GET /datasets - returns the list of datasets and factors, used to initialize the UI
- GET /scores/{nuts_id} - returns raw data for the specified NUTS region
- POST /scores - computes and returns scores for all the NUTS regions based on the requested factors, datasets and their weights

Method POST /scores

Request - JSON data specifying the factors and datasets for which the scores are being requested, e.g.

```
{
  "factors": [
    { "factor": "Social & Human", "weight": 1,
      "datasets": ["S_Satisfaction_1", "S_Young"] },
    { "factor": "Natural", "weight": 0.5,
      "datasets": ["N_Greenhouse"] }
  ]
}
```

Response - JSON data with computed scores for all the NUTS regions in the CSV data file; the computation takes into account the requested datasets and the factor weights

```
[
  {
    "code": "DE254",
    "Social & Human": 0.4596110712213411,
    "Natural": 0.8094358906617971,
    "aggregate": 0.6653903767745506
  },
  {
```

```

"code": "DE255",
"Social & Human": 0.44303916292050893,
"Natural": 0.8063307389327923,
"aggregate": 0.656740089986558
},
...
]
    
```

8.1.3 User interface

Figure 20 Interface for Attractiveness calculation

In the analysis panel it is possible to adjust the factor weights using sliders. The map updates automatically coloring the regions according to RdYIGn divergent colormap. (Figure 19)

Figure 21 Region Data Visualisation

After the user hovers over a NUTS region, he or she can see how the total score is calculated and the values of factors before weights are applied. (Figure 20)

8.2 Region clustering

8.2.1 Algorithmus development

The data are clustered through several algorithms provided by R software. Algorithms were tested for 12 clusters (derived from Struges’ principle). 19 optimized and normalized data describing particular factors of rural attractiveness were used as input data. The optimization is based on qualified selection following weights (importance) of particular factors of rural attractiveness, quality of data, semantics (and relation to rural attractiveness) as well as mutual correlation of particular datasets.

Following table and images present different views on clustering of regions.

Type of clustering	Hierarchical	Non-hierarchical
Method	Agglomerative	Hartigan-Wong
Parameter	Distances: Manhattan	Number of restarts: 50

Table 2 Region clustering

8.2.2 Front end development

Front end is under development and will be implemented in next stage

8.3 Best Practice Atlas

The ENABLING project (www.enabling-project.com) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 774578. The Enabling project intends to develop the great potential of the bio-based industry, encouraging the creation of efficient and structured biomass supply chains for the production of bio-based products (BBP). To do so, ENABLING proposes tools and methodologies nurturing collaboration and knowledge transfer among practitioners in the sector, through the creation of physical and virtual spaces for sharing best practices, brokering innovation in the bio-economy and providing stakeholders with coaching and guidance on innovation. As one from applications, which we integrated into the PoliRural Hub as a module, can help to European Regional Policymakers to support the circular economy in EU regions.

In ENABLING was collected best BBP (Bio based Products and Processes) practices, from inside and outside Europe, that are wholly or partly transferable to other regions, or serve as an inspiration for partners in the value chain. An interactive web based tool will provide easy to find information on the best practices identified. Best Practices sheets are produced to summarise the information gathered and provided in the appropriate format for upload to the EIP Agri platform. A thorough check is performed by partners on the compliance of the information provided with the format required by EIP Agri. This activity is coordinated and the harmonisation of content and its compliance with the EIP Agri platform is ensured by Task leader euknow. The Best Practices Atlas (WIRELESSINFO) – an interactive web based tool providing easy to find information on the best practices identified.

The Best Practices Atlas (BPA) visualizes best practices identified on a map and provides easily accessible information to inform and inspire other stakeholders active in the Biobased network. Examples of Best practices are, as part of the Enabling project, collected by all project partners from individual countries. There is therefore a huge need to identify, synthesise, share and present good practices in the field of biomass supply management and provide the opportunity for new BBPs pathways. Enabling will organise and carry out the identification of about 100 good practices across Europe and other parts of the world and provide them to the beneficiaries in the common format foreseen by the EIP-AGRI commission for Sustainable and Productive Agriculture. (Figure 21).

PoliRural adaptation of the Best Practice Atlas will be populated with case studies of new entrants to raise awareness about their experiences, challenges and success factors. The PoliRural BPA can be found on a separate website <https://atlasbestpractices.com/polirural/> and is also embedded in PolRural DIH - <https://hub.polirural.eu/best-practises>.

Figure 22 Best Practice Atlas I

These examples will be visualized on the map with a detailed description and linked to the map in form of some mark (pin). From the beginning, the Best Practices Atlas will be implemented in the Enabling project website as a simple link, in the next phase as an embedded window. (Figure 22)

Figure 23 Best Practice Atlas II

9 How to access

9.1 Open Access

Portal URL: <https://hub.polirural.eu/home>

All information for reading and visualisation are Open and available for registration. All visitors are able to become regular portal users with the rights for editing and creating new content. Creating a new account is allowed for all visitors.

9.2 Administration for frontend users

Registered users are allowed to edit some information and create content. (Figure 23)

Figure 24 Administration menu for registered users

The left menu provides you options for editing user account information and logout. (Figure 24).

9.3 Pilot sections

Each of 12 pilot sites are given a dedicated space to introduce their region and describe priority issues addressed and ways how to reach the defined expected outcome. Detailed description can be found to each of the pilots including needs gathering table, progress bar chart, map and event calendar to promote coming events. Training for the pilots was organized to demonstrate the administration of the pilot site should the pilot express interest for that.

Figure 25 Editing menu

9.4 Account setting

Account setting allows you to edit: (Figure 25)

- your personal information
- information about your organisation
- check portal information
- change password

General **Contact** Preferences

Information
Organizations
Memberships
Roles
Password

Information

PERSONAL INFORMATION

<p>Screen Name *</p> <input type="text" value="petrtest"/>	
<p>Email Address *</p> <input type="text" value="uhlir@wirelessinfo.cz"/>	
<p>Language</p> <input type="text" value="English (United States)"/>	<p>User ID</p> <input type="text" value="51933"/>
<p>Prefix</p> <input type="text"/>	<p>Job Title</p> <input type="text"/>
<p>First Name *</p> <input type="text" value="Petr"/>	
<p>Middle Name</p> <input type="text"/>	

Figure 26 Profile of user setting

9.5 Editing social media and tools

9.5.1 Content and Knowledge base - Science Shop

9.5.1.1 Knowledge base > Science shop

Science shop will help make contact between researchers and users; it is the space for demand and supply - new projects, thesis, research, processing ideas, etc. Science shop is a kind of forum which allows signed in users to create new posts. (Figure 26)

Figure 27 Science shop

For adding new thread just go to the particular category and add New Thread (Figure 27)

Figure 28 Science shop - adding new thread

Figure 29 Science shop - thread example

The thread can be also edited, deleted or can be replied to. (Figure 28)

9.5.2 Forum

9.5.2.1 Knowledge base > Forum

Forum is a space for exchanging short information and experiences with other users and is divided into categories. Forum has a similar functionality as a Science shop above, it means that the users are able to add new thread, edit thread, delete thread and add new answers.

This forum is a utility for creating a moderated knowledge base.

9.5.3 Wiki

9.5.3.1 Knowledge base > wiki

Wiki is used for sharing knowledge collected by users. It is a typical citizen's science tool. Liferay Portal's Wiki is a full-featured wiki application which has all the features you would expect in a state of the art wiki. (Figure 29)

Figure 30 Wiki - adding new page

Figure 31 Wiki - short codes

OPTIONS:

- Categorization - Tags for searching
- Related Assets
- Configuration - coding type
- Permissions

9.5.4 Blog

9.5.4.1 Knowledge base > Blog

Blog is a tool that contains user posts on the specific page. Blog posts are displayed in reverse chronological order (i.e., the most recent top) and are assigned to category.

The Blog tool has a complete set of WYSIWYG controls that appear when and where the user needs them. Users can use WYSIWYG editor for text styling, adding images / files and other formatting. Editor can be also switched to source mode to edit content's HTML code. The Blog also contains a powerful set of tools for customizing. (Figure 31).

Figure 32 Blog - Adding new post

9.6 Access to JupyterHub

JupyterHub is a multiuser interface to the Jupyter Notebook accessible on <https://polirural-jupyter.lesprojekt.cz/> Unlike the Jupyter Notebook it allows for simultaneous work of many users on a single machine. Send a request to polirural-jupyter@lesprojekt.cz to get access to JupyterHub. Your credentials would then be sent to your email.

Figure 33 Jupyter Notebook access

JupyterHub maintains user generated files (i.e. notebooks) and their generation in the web browser environment, all the calculations run on the server. Users manage their notebooks using the web interface. (Figure 32)

Python 3 kernel is available including mathematical, statistical and spatial data manipulation and visualisation libraries. These are Numpy, Rasterio, GeoPandas and many others. (Figure 33)

Figure 34 Visualisation data with Jupyter

Users can access JupyterHub from the internet, using any device having an internet browser, which enables excellent variability and mobility for users. All calculations are made on the server and users can benefit from much higher performance than it would be when running Jupyter on their own PC.

10 Conclusion

The first edition of the PoliRural DIH has been implemented and is available to the pilot localities and the public. The system was internally tested and it is ready for use inside the PoliRural project, pilot sites have been implemented and are continuously updated in the close cooperation with pilot localities representants as the project implementation goes on. The DIH development will continue in the next period according to specification from D3.1.

Another more important task is to build a community around the PoliRural DIH. This is the most critical issue for the next period. We plan to use more possibilities how to attract potential users:

- Start with publishing attractive content
- Promote the DIH and its content via social networks and another online marketing tools
- Attract visitors to become a regular DIH user
- Find and communicate motivation factors for new users
- Support new and regular users with developing new tools and applications
- Communicate actively with stakeholders in pilots
- Organise promotional campaigns such as hackathons